

Effect of Yoga and Meditation in Human Life Span

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Introduction:

The art of practicing yoga **helps in controlling an individual's mind, body and soul**. It brings together physical and mental disciplines to achieve a peaceful body and mind; it helps manage stress and anxiety and keeps you relaxing. It also helps in increasing flexibility, muscle strength and body tone. Yoga is not a religion, it is a way of living that aims towards a healthy mind in a healthy body. Man is a physical, mental and spiritual being; yoga helps promote a balanced development of all the three. Other forms of physical exercises, like aerobics, assure only physical well-being. They have little to do with the development of the spiritual or astral body. Yoga is often partially understood as being limited to asanas or poses, and its benefits are only perceived to be at the physical level. However, we fail to realize the immense benefits yoga offers in uniting the body, mind, and breath. When you are in harmony, the journey through life is calmer, happier and more fulfilling. So, if you are keen to lose weight, develop a strong and flexible body or being at peace, then yoga can help you achieve it all.

Benefits of yog

1. Yoga helps you in all-around fitness

As Gurudev Sri Sri Ravi Shankar puts it, "Health is not a mere absence of disease. It is a dynamic expression of life – in terms of how joyful, loving, and enthusiastic you are." Yoga poses, pranayama (breathing techniques) and meditation are a holistic fitness package. The benefits accrued by being a regular practitioner are numerous. Some very discernible ones are:

- Improves health

- Gives mental strength
- Improves physical strength
- Protects from injury
- Detoxifies the body

2. Yoga benefits in weight loss

Sun Salutation and Kapal Bhati pranayama are highly useful for losing weight. Moreover, with regular practice of yoga, we tend to become more sensitive to our body and its needs. This, in turn, helps keep a check on our food intake and body weight.

3. Yoga is one of the best solutions for stress relief

A few minutes of yoga daily can be a great way to get rid of stress, both in body and mind. Yoga postures, pranayama, and meditation are effective techniques to release stress.

4. Yoga helps for inner peace

We all love to visit peaceful, serene spots that are rich in natural beauty. Little do we realize that peace can be found right within us and we can take a mini vacation to experience this any time of the day. Yoga is also one of the best ways to calm a disturbed mind.

5. Yoga Improves Immunity

Our system is a seamless blend of the body, mind, and spirit. An irregularity in the body affects the mind and similarly, unpleasantness or restlessness in the mind can manifest as an ailment in the body. Yoga poses help massage organs and strengthens muscles while breathing techniques and meditation release stress and improve immunity.

6. Practice of Yoga Offers Greater Awareness

The mind is constantly involved in an activity – swinging from the past to the future – but never staying in present. By simply being aware of mind's tendency, we can save ourselves from getting stressed or worked up. Yoga and pranayama help create that awareness and bring the mind back to the present moment, where it can stay happy and focused.

7. Yoga improves relationships

Yoga can even help improve your relationship with your loved ones. A mind that is relaxed, happy and content is better able to deal with sensitive relationship matters. Yoga and meditation aids in keeping the mind happy and peaceful. Gradually, you will also notice an improvement in your relations with those around you.

8. Yoga Increases Energy

Do you feel completely drained by the end of the day? Shuttling through chores and multitasking continuously can be quite exhausting. A few minutes of yoga every day boosts our energy level and keeps us fresh. A 10-minute online guided meditation in the middle of a hectic day is all you need to charge up your batteries.

9. Yoga Gives you Better Flexibility and Posture

Yoga must become a part of your daily routine to get a body that is strong, supple, and flexible. Regular yoga practice stretches and tones the body muscles and also makes them strong. It also helps improve your body posture when you stand, sit, sleep or walk. This would, in turn, help relieve you of body ache due to incorrect posture.

10. Yoga helps in improving intuition

Yoga and meditation have the power to improve your intuitive ability so that you spontaneously realize what needs to be done, when and how, to yield positive results. Since Yoga is a continuous process, it is recommended to keep practicing. The deeper you go into yoga practice, the more profound its benefits will be.

Meditation

Meditation can give you a sense of calm, peace and balance that can benefit both your emotional well-being and your overall health. You can also use it to relax and cope with stress by refocusing your attention on something calming. Meditation can help you learn to stay centered and keep inner peace.

Benefits of Meditation for mental health.

Meditation establishes a secure connection between our internal and external worlds. It awakens the body and benefits all aspects of the conscious and subconscious layers of the mind. Out of the numerous perks that meditation gives, a few are listed below

1. Meditation enhances empathy

Loving-kindness or compassion meditation fires neural connections to brain sites that regulate positive emotions like empathy and kindness. The deep state of flow that meditation induces builds social connectedness and make us more affectionate and amicable as a person.

2. Meditation improves cognition

Researchers agree that an excellent way for professionals to increase the likelihood of success is to keep meditation practice as a part of their daily routine. Studies have revealed that both transcendent and mindful meditation practices improve the brain's problem-solving and decision-making strategies, which can bring a desirable shift in our professional life.

3. Meditation is a natural stress stabilizer

Stress is the body's response to unforeseen adversities. Encountering immediate threats increase the level of cortisol, or stress hormone in the body, and activates the Autonomic Nervous system, which is responsible for fight-or-flight responses. Brain studies of regular meditators revealed that they have lower cortisol level in their brains, which explains their resilience and insightful nature.

4. Meditation promotes emotional health and well-being

Studies have shown that meditation improves self-image and self-worth. When we meditate, we get a clear picture of our mind and become aware of the thoughts that drive our emotions and actions at the moment.

A large-scale study found that regular meditation decreases the likelihood of developing depression and mood-related disorders (Jain, Walsh, Eisendrath, Christensen, & Cahn, 2015). Besides some forms of meditative practices which also promoted positive thinking, as researchers stated, and could improve the overall emotional health of an individual.

5. Meditation increases attention by inducing a state of flow

Have you noticed how meditation absorbs you into the moment? Mindful awareness comes naturally to us when we meditate, and we reach 'flow' state where our mind is in complete harmony with itself. A study on the effects of an eight-week mindful meditation course found that people who are regular meditation practitioners had heightened attention and concentration span.

Conclusion:

Practicing Yoga and Meditation helps develop the body and mind, yet is not a substitute for medicine. It is essential to *learn and practice yoga and Meditation under the supervision of a trained Yoga teacher. In case of any medical condition, practice yoga only after consulting your doctor and a Sri Sri Yoga teacher.*

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